

Relationship between Profile and Food Consumption Pattern of Tribal Families of Palghar District

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Abstract— This paper examines the relationship between profile and food consumption pattern of the tribal families from Palghar district. The study was conducted at the Palghar district. Samples of 120 tribal families were considered as respondents for present study. The respondents were interviewed with the help of specially designed schedule. Collected data was classified, tabulated and analysed by using various statistical methods. The result of the study showed that the relationship between family education status and food consumption pattern, family size and food consumption pattern, annual income of the family and food consumption pattern, cropping pattern and food consumption pattern, resource availability and food consumption pattern was found to be 'positive' and 'significant'. The relationship between major occupation and food consumption pattern, land holding and food consumption pattern, farming experience and food consumption pattern, social participation and food consumption pattern was found to be 'non-significant'. The extension workers should consider these facts while planning and executing programmes for development of the tribal families living in Palghar district.

Keywords— Profile, Food consumption pattern, tribal families, Relationship.

I. INTRODUCTION

India has the second largest tribal population in the world, next to Africa. Our country represents over 700 tribal groups (including sub-groups) with a population of 84.3 million (8.2%) population in almost all states except in Haryana and Punjab. Bhil, Gond-Madia, Katkari, Koli, Oraon, Warli are the major tribes of Maharashtra. These communities are mostly dependent on wild plants for many purposes. The tribal communities have vast knowledge about the importance of consumption of wild plants. Nutritional status of the population largely depends on the consumption of food in relation to their needs, which is influenced by availability of food and purchasing power. With respect to food consumption, people living in urban areas have better access to variety of food items while tribal people living in remote and isolated areas have different dietary habits. The choice of food is deeply related to the lifestyle of an individual. Food habits and consumption pattern is greatly influenced by thoughts, beliefs, notions, traditions and taboos of the society. Apart from these socio-cultural barriers, the religion, education, and economic factors do alter the food behaviour. Maharashtra is becoming one of the game-changers in agriculture-nutrition in India. For one component of the Grand Challenge Initiative funded by Biotechnology Industry Research Assistance Council (BIRAC) and the Gates Foundation, MSSRF has been working to address malnutrition through the underlying cause of agriculture, gender and biofortification. Food consumption pattern of the tribes needs to be assessed because it helps us understand the major effect on the nutritional status of the population. Also, there is an urgent need to document the data regarding consumption pattern of food that will give an understanding of the existing health. Also, there is a need to spread awareness about the health care and food consumption pattern through educational programmes in the tribal areas. The intervention of these programmes can help them identify their problems and find an appropriate solution for these problems.

II. OBJECTIVE

To ascertain the relationship between profile and food consumption pattern of the tribal families

III. METHODOLOGY

The research work was conducted in Palghar district of Konkan region of Maharashtra state because it has maximum tribal population in the Konkan region. Two tahsils Mokhada and Vikramgad having maximum tribal population were selected to carry out the research. Six villages from each tahsil were selected randomly to carry out the present study. A total of 120 tribal families were considered as respondents for the present study. The data was collected with the help of a specially designed interview schedule by keeping in view the objective of the study. To determine the relationship among the independent and dependent variables correlation analysis was worked out. For the study nine independent variables namely Family education status (X1), Family size (X2), Annual income of family (X3), Major occupation (X4), Land holding (X5),

Cropping pattern (X5), Farming experience (X6), Social participation (X6) and Resource availability (X7) were selected and their relationship with dependent variable food consumption pattern was worked out. 'Ex-post facto' research design was used to conduct the present study.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The predictive power of each variable was estimated by working out the value of co-efficient of determination (R^2). Independent variables together contributed 26.00 per cent variation in the food consumption pattern of the tribal families. This implies that the selected independent variables explained the variation in the food consumption pattern of tribal families to the extent of 26.00 per cent.

TABLE 1
CORRELATION COEFFICIENT OF INDEPENDENT VARIABLES WITH FOOD CONSUMPTION PATTERN

S. No.	Independent Variables	Variable Code	Correlation coefficient (r)
1.	Family education status	X1	0.21456 *
2.	Family size	X2	0.21549 *
3.	Annual income of family	X3	0.31835 *
4.	Major occupation	X4	-0.05055 NS
5.	Land holding	X5	0.17250 NS
6.	Cropping pattern	X6	0.27477 *
7.	Farming experience	X7	-0.04462 NS
8.	Social participation	X8	-0.01762 NS
9.	Resource availability	X9	0.29027 *

$$R^2 = 0.2600 \quad F = 4.296$$

*= Significant at 0.05 level

NS = Non significant

- The correlation coefficient computed between Family education status (X1) and food consumption pattern (Y1) at 0.05 level of significance is 0.21456 which is greater than the table value 0.174.
- A significant and positive relationship was found between Family size (X2) and food consumption pattern (Y1) at 0.05 level of significance. The correlation coefficient computed is 0.21549 which is greater than the table value 0.174.
- The correlation coefficient computed between Annual family income (X3) and food consumption pattern (Y1) at 0.05 level of significance is 0.31835 which is greater than the table value 0.174.
- The correlation coefficient computed between Major occupation (X4) and food consumption pattern (Y1) at 0.05 level of significance is -0.05055 which is less than the table value 0.174.
- The correlation coefficient computed between Land holding (X5) and food consumption pattern (Y1) at 0.05 level of significance is 0.17250 which is less than the table value 0.174.
- The correlation coefficient computed between Cropping pattern (X6) and food consumption pattern (Y1) at 0.05 level of significance is 0.27477 which is greater than the table value 0.174.
- The correlation coefficient computed between Farming experience (X7) and food consumption pattern (Y1) at 0.05 level of significance is -0.04462 which is less than the table value 0.174.
- The correlation coefficient computed between Social participation (X8) and food consumption pattern (Y1) at 0.05 level of significance is -0.01762 which is less than the table value 0.174.
- The correlation coefficient computed between Resource availability (X9) and food consumption pattern (Y1) at 0.05 level of significance is 0.29027 which is greater than the table value 0.174.

V. CONCLUSION

The result of the study showed that the relationship between family education status and food consumption pattern, family size and food consumption pattern, annual income of the family and food consumption pattern, cropping pattern and food consumption pattern, resource availability and food consumption pattern was found to be 'positive' and 'significant'. The relationship between major occupation and food consumption pattern, land holding and food consumption pattern, farming experience and food consumption pattern, social participation and food consumption pattern was found to be 'non-

significant'. The extension workers should consider these facts while planning and executing programmes for development of the tribal families living in Palghar district.

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